

Fig S1. Artificial contour dynamics based on our model with comparison of underlying contour propagation and contour mapping. First, the contour is propagated by the model function f evaluated for an equidistant set of grid points on the contour (green dashed trajectories). Secondly, the protrusion component X_{prot} is propagated by a strongly regularized flow to avoid thinning and clustering effects of virtual markers (blue dashed trajectories). This contour mapping can then be used as underlying coordinate system in kymograph representations.